

Synthesis, Spectroscopic Properties and Antileishmanial Screening of some Pentamidine Analogues

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Pentamidine, the diamidine drug of choice is used for the treatment of antimony resistant leishmanial infection. A modified method for preparation of the water-soluble isethionate salt of pentamidine has been developed using *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde as starting material. Beside the synthesis of the dimethoxy analogues of pentamidine hydrochloride and pentamidine isethionate, two compounds have been prepared by substitution of amidino groups of pentamidine and its dimethoxy analogue by imidazoline moieties. Cmr spectral data of the compounds have been assigned and the *in vitro* antileishmanial activity of the analogues were compared with pentamidine isethionate using *Leishmania donovani* UR-6 strain.

Pentamidine synthesised by Ashley *et al.*¹ in 1942, is the diamidine of choice for the treatment of leishmaniasis as well as the African trypanosomiasis². It is also used as an effective agent for the treatment of *Pneumocystis carinii pneumonia* (PCP)³. In the usual method pentamidine is prepared from *p*-aminophenol which is converted to *p*-cyanophenol by the Sandmeyer reaction. It is difficult to obtain pure *p*-aminophenol which is readily oxidised under ordinary conditions. Moreover, the yield of *p*-cyanophenol obtained from *p*-aminophenol by the Sandmeyer reaction is not good. *p*-Cyanophenol is used to prepare 4,4'-dicyano- α,ω -diphenoxypentane by the action of pentamethylene dibromide and subsequently this dicyano compound is converted to pentamidine¹. This diamidine has its most particular worth in various strains of *Leishmania donovani* which show relative resistant to antimonials.

In the present method, *p*-cyanophenol has been obtained in good yield from *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde for the first time although the conversion of an aromatic aldehyde to the cyano derivative is known⁴. The other steps involving the conversion of *p*-cyanophenol to pentamidine isethionate were performed in the usual way⁵. The various steps involved in the process are shown in Scheme 1. The different parameters involving the different steps were standardised for better yield of the end-product.

The dimethoxy analogues of pentamidine hydrochloride as well as pentamidine isethionate were prepared using vanillin as the starting material. The imidazoline derivatives were synthesised by refluxing the methanolic solution of the corresponding imino-ether hydrochloride with ethylene diamine. Although the effectiveness of the imidazoline moiety has not been examined in leishmanial infection its efficacy in experimental PCP has been reported^{6,7}. All the compounds were characterised by their pmr as well as cmr spectral data and for the analogues by elemental analyses. The cmr data of the compounds are reported for the first time (Table 1) and were assigned taking into consideration the known chemical shift rules⁸, substituent effects and by comparison with those of the compounds with similar carbon atoms.

Antileishmanial activity : RPMI-1640 medium was used to test the antileishmanial activity *in vitro* against the promastigotes of *L. donovani* (UR-6 strain). *L. donovani* parasites were taken from modified Ray's solid blood agar slant after culturing 72 h for each experiment. 2.5×10^8 parasites were suspended in RPMI-1640 medium (1 ml) and 1 mM of each compound was added separately to it in a constant volume. Tubes were incubated at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ for 2-6 h and viability of the parasites

Scheme 1

was checked by microscope using haemocytometer. The results are reported in Table 2. We are pursuing our studies with regard to in vivo antileishmanial activity of the analogues as well as their relative toxicity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid-bath and are uncorrected. Homogeneity of the

compounds was routinely checked on silica gel-G tlc plates. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and pmr and cmr spectra were obtained with a JEOL FT-100 spectrometer at 100 and 25.05 MHz respectively with TMS as an internal standard.

p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (**2a**): Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (8.6 g, 0.14 mol) and sodium hydroxide

TABLE 1-CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS* (δ) OF 7, 8a, 8b AND 9b IN DMSO-d₆

Carbon no	7	8a	8b	9b
1,1'	148.8	163.0	149.0	148.0
2,2'	153.0	114.8	153.0	153.0
3,3'	111.8	130.0	111.8	110.3
4,4'	118.8	119.2	122.1	122.9
5,5'	121.9	130.0	119.3	119.5
6,6'	112.6	114.8	112.8	111.6
∞, ω	68.6	68.0	68.8	68.4
$\beta \delta$	28.9	28.0	28.2	28.5
γ	22.0	21.9	22.2	22.2
Amidino carbons	164.7	164.7	164.8	164.4
Imidazolino carbons	-	-	-	49.9
OCH ₃	56.2	-	56.1	55.7
CH ₂ OH	-	57.5	57.6	-
CH ₂ SO ₃ H	-	53.8	53.9	-

* Multiplicity of the signals were determined by off-resonance and INEPT studies

(5.6 g; 0.14 mol) were dissolved in minimum volume of water and added to the ethanolic solution (120 ml) of **1a** (12.2 g, 0.10 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, cooled and worked up as usual to give **2a** (10 g, 77%), m.p. 70°.

4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldoxime (2b) : Compound **2b** (13.1 g, 79%), m.p. 106°, was prepared by similar procedure from vanillin (15.2 g, 0.10 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (8.6 g, 0.14 mol).

p-Cyanophenol (3a) : Compound **2a** (10 g, 0.07 mol) dissolved in acetic anhydride (30 ml), was refluxed for 1 h. After cooling, the solution was poured into ice-water when white crystalline compound (10.2 g, 82%), m.p. 60° was separated out as *p*-acetoxybenzotrile, ν_{\max} 2 200 cm⁻¹ (CN).

TABLE 2-RELATIVE ANTILEISHMANIAL EFFICACY OF 7, 8a, 8b AND 9b

Compd no	Percentage of parasite killing		
	2 h	4 h	6 h
7	67.0	76.0	79.0
8a	83.3	95.2	97.7
8b	72.2	85.0	89.0
9b	38.0	56.0	73.0

A 4% KOH solution (50 ml) was added to the ethanolic solution of the latter, warmed for 15–20 min and allowed to stand. Acidification and usual work-up furnished **3a** (6.2 g, 88%), m.p. 112° (lit.⁹. 110–13°).

2-Methoxy-4-cyanophenol (3b) : Compound **3b** (9.64 g, 82%), m.p. 88° (lit.¹⁰. 89–90°) was prepared similarly from **2b** (13.1 g, 0.09 mol).

4,4'-Dicyano- α, ω -diphenoxypentane (4a) : An aqueous solution (30 ml) of sodium hydroxide (4.6 g, 0.10 mol) was added to the ethanolic solution (100 ml) of **3a** (12 g, 0.10 mol), and refluxed for 1 h. Then pentamethylene dibromide (8 ml, 0.05 mol) was added to the resulting solution of sodium 4-cyanophenoxide, refluxing was continued for 3 h and worked up as usual. The crude dicyano compound was crystallised from ethanol as white needles (10.4 g, 68%), m.p. 112°; ν_{\max} 2 220 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 7.56 (4H, dd, *J* 2, 8 Hz, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 6.90 (4H, dd, *J* 2, 8 Hz, 2,2', 6,6'-H), 4.0 (4H, t, *J* 4 Hz, 2 × OCH₂) and 1.64 (6H, m, 3 × CH₂).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-4,4'-dicyano- α, ω -diphenoxypentane (4b) : Compound **4b** (8 g, 67%), m.p. 130°, was similarly prepared from **3b** (9.6 g, 0.07 mol) and pentamethylene dibromide (6 ml, 0.04 mol); ν_{\max} 2 210 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 7.26 (2H, dd, *J* 2, 8 Hz, 5,5'-H), 7.06 (2H, d, *J* 2 Hz, 3,3'-H), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 6,6'-H), 4.08 (4H, t, *J* 4 Hz, 2 × OCH₂), 3.86 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃) and 1.96 (6H, m, 3 × CH₂).

Imino-ether hydrochloride of α, ω -diphenoxypentane (5a) : Compound **4a** (7.5 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in dry CHCl₃ (100 ml) and dry EtOH (50 ml). The mixture was saturated by passing dry HCl gas with stirring at 5–10°. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 7 days when an amorphous solid was separated out. Compound **5a** (7 g, 64%), m.p. 234°d, was collected by filtration, washed with alcohol and dried; ν_{\max} 3 390 and 3 150 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.88 (4H, m, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 7.00 (4H, m, 2,2', 6,6'-H),

4.28 (4H, q, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.08 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 2.00–1.52 (6H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2$) and 1.32 (6H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

Imino-ether hydrochloride of 2,2'-dimethoxy- α,ω -diphenoxypentane (5b): Compound **5b** (6.2 g, 62%), m.p. 250° , was similarly prepared from **4b** (7 g, 0.02 mol); ν_{max} 3 410 and 3 200 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.84 (2H, dd, J 2, 8 Hz, 5,5'-H), 7.70 (2H, d, J 2 Hz, 3,3'-H), 7.20 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 6,6'-H), 4.66 (4H, q, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.16 (4H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 3.88 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 1.86 (6H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2$) and 1.50 (6H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$).

Imino-ether base of α,ω -diphenoxypentane(6a): Compound **4a** (6 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in dry CHCl_3 (100 ml) and dry ethanol (50 ml), and after saturation with dry HCl gas the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 7 days and then run into crushed ice followed by the addition of 50% aqueous NaOH solution until the mixture was alkaline to phenolphthalein. The organic layer was separated and distilled to yield **6a** (6 g, 77%), m.p. 60° .

Imino-ether base of 2,2'-dimethoxy- α,ω -diphenoxypentane (6b): Compound **6b** (6.8 g, 76%), m.p. 85° , was prepared by similar procedure from **4b** (7 g, 0.02 mol).

Pentamidine isethionate (8a): A solution of ammonium isethionate (4.3 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in minimum volume of water, was added to the ethanolic solution (30 ml) of **6a** (5 g, 0.012 mol). The mixture was stirred for 24 h at $45\text{--}50^\circ$. The solvent was then removed by distillation and the residue on treatment with acetone afforded **8a** (5.9 g, 83%), m.p. 177° (lit.⁵ 180°); ν_{max} 3 400–3 100 cm^{-1} (OH, NH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 8.98 (6H, brd, D_2O exchangeable, $6 \times \text{NH}$), 7.88 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 7.19 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, 2,2', 6,6'-H), 4.48 (4H, br, D_2O exchangeable, $4 \times \text{OH}$), 4.16 (4H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 3.68 (4H, q, J 6 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 2.68 (4H, t, J 8 Hz,

2,2'-Dimethoxypentamidine isethionate (8b): Compound **8b** (1.8 g, 66%), m.p. 155° (Found : C, 46.12; H, 6.09; N, 8.50. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires : C, 46.01; H, 6.13; N, 8.58%), was prepared similarly from **6b** (2 g, 0.004 mol) and ammonium isethionate (1.2 g, 0.008 mol); ν_{max} 3 390–3 150 cm^{-1} (OH, NH); δ ((DMSO- d_6) 9.36–8.52 (6H, br, D_2O exchangeable, $6 \times \text{NH}$), 7.52 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 5,5'-H), 7.44 (2H, d, J 2 Hz, 3,3'-H), 7.22 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 6,6'-H), 4.48 (4H, br, D_2O exchangeable, $4 \times \text{OH}$), 4.12 (4H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 3.88 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 3.70 (4H, q, J 6 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 2.66 (4H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) and 2.08–1.40 (6H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2$).

2,2'-Dimethoxypentamidine hydrochloride (7): Dry and powdered **5b** (0.8 g, 0.002 mol) was stirred with 10% absolute ethanolic ammonia (50 ml) at 0° for 3–4 h and kept overnight. After usual work up, compound **7** (0.52 g, 86%), m.p. 240°d (Found : C, 53.20; H, 6.29; N, 11.78. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires : C, 53.27; H, 6.34; N, 11.83%), was isolated; ν_{max} 3 340 and 3 100 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 9.22 (6H, brd, D_2O exchangeable, $6 \times \text{NH}$), 7.56 (4H, m, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 7.16 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 6,6'-H), 4.12 (4H, t, J 4 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 3.88 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$) and 1.72 (6H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2$).

4,4'-Diimidazolino- α,ω -diphenoxypentanehydrochloride (9a): The methanolic solution (50 ml) of **5a** (2 g, 0.004 mol) was refluxed with ethylene diamine (16 ml, 0.008 mol) for 3–4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and compound **9a** (1.8 g, 58%), m.p. 238°d (Found : C, 59.21; H, 6.39; N, 12.10. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$ requires : C, 59.35; H, 6.45; N, 12.04%), was crystallised from ethanol; ν_{max} 3 330 and 3 125 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.85 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 7.16 (2H, br, D_2O exchangeable, $2 \times \text{NH}$), 6.97 (4H, d, J 8 Hz, 2,2', 6,6'-H), 4.04 (8H, t, J

4 Hz, 2 × OCH₂ and (-CH₂)₂-N) and 2.00–1.44 (6H, m, 3 × CH₂).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-4,4'-diimidazolino- α , ω -diphenoxypentane hydrochloride (9b) : Compound **9b** (1.6 g, 57%), m.p. 230^o (Found : C, 57.02 : H, 6.40; N, 10.58. C₂₅H₃₄O₄N₄Cl₂ requires : C, 57.14; H, 6.47; N, 10.66%), was similarly prepared from **6b** (2 g, 0.004 mol) and ethylene diamine (16 ml, 0.008 mol); ν_{\max} 3 350 and 3 120 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.64 (2H, brs, D₂O exchangeable, 2 × NH), 7.52 (4H, m, 3,3', 5,5'-H), 7.16 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 6,6'-H), 4.12 (8H, t, *J* 4 Hz, 2 × OCH₂ and (-CH₂)₂-N=), 3.84 (5H, s, 2 × OCH₃) and 2.04–1.40 (6H, m, 3 × CH₂).

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